

**DETERMINATION OF ORGANOGENESIS IN LOCAL COWPEA
(*Vigna unguiculata*) L. (WALP) VARIETIES USING EXCISED EMBRYO
INVITRO.**

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Abstract-: Organogenesis in vitro was evaluated in explants derived from excised embryo of four cowpea varieties cultured on Murashige and Skoog (MS) basal medium. To evaluate the response of the cowpea genotypes to in vitro regeneration, seedlings were derived from zygotic embryos excised from surface sterilized seeds after two weeks of culture on MS basalmedium + vitamins supplement with 35% sucrose. The varieties used were Danila and Kanannado obtained from local farmers. The result shows that Danila has the highest response with 90% producing shoot apices more than 1cm, followed by Kanannado with 75% producing apices more than 1cm. The result shows that, the two local varieties used have good response to Organogenesis and the shoot apices produced can be subjected to Somatic embryogenesis to evaluate shoots production and possible transformation in to calli.

Keyword: Organogenesis, Somatic Embryogenesis, Explants, Seedlings, Callus

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1.0 Introduction

Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp) is a staple food crop of significance worldwide. Major diversity in cowpea is found in Asia and Africa, but the precise origin of cowpea has been a matter of speculation and discussion for many years. Early observations showed that cowpea genotypes in Asia is very diverse and morphologically different from those in Africa. Therefore, both Asia and Africa were thought to be independent centers of origin of cowpea (Horn L. N., 2020).

However, in the absence of wild cowpeas in Asia as possible progenitors, Asian center of origin has recently been questioned. All the current evidence suggests that cowpea originated in southern Africa although it is difficult to ascertain where in Africa the crop was first domesticated. Several centers of domestication have been suggested. These include Ethiopia, Central Africa, South Africa and West Africa. Based on the distribution of diverse wild cowpea in Eastern Africa stretching from Ethiopia to Southern Africa, the working group meeting of the International Board for Plant Genetics Resources on *Vigna* held in New Delhi in 1981 recommend as a priority, collection of both wild and cultivated forms of cowpea in Southern Africa, Zimbabwe, Transvaal and Natal. East and Southern Africa are considered as the primary regions of diversity and West and Central Africa to be the secondary centers of diversity. India in particular and Asia in general have been proposed to be the third centers of diversity (Togola A., 2023).

Recent investigations by the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) in collaboration with Institute of Germoplasma (CNR) Bari, Italy strongly indicate that the region encompassing Namibia, Botswana, Zambia, Zimbabwe, Mozambique, Swaziland and South Africa have the highest genetic diversity in respect of primitive wild forms of cowpea. Some very primitive species were

observed in the Transvaal, Cape Town and Swaziland. Based on this, it has been suggested that southern Africa may be the center of origin of cowpea and from there to Asia and West Africa. Cowpea was known in India before Christ and it has Sanskrit name in early treatise dating back to 150BC. Cowpea must have moved from east Africa to Asia more than 2000 years ago where human selection led to modified forms of cowpea different from Africa (Ali Amir *et al*, 2008). It has been suggested that cowpea probably moved from Eastern Africa to India before 150BC to West Asia and Europe about 300 BC and to Americas in 1500 AD (Brar *et al*, 1999). Since western Asia and Europe do not have desired climatic conditions for cowpea cultivation, not much variability and selection occurred as it happened in South Asia and South East Asia, where small seeded and vegetable Cowpea were selected. Probably, the wild cowpeas with very small seed were distributed by birds in east and west Africa much before Christian era and therefore the presence there of great diversity and secondary wild forms. Selection for larger seeds and better growth habits from natural variants in wild cowpeas by humans must have led to diverse culti groups and their domestication in Asia and in Africa (Nwagboso, C. 2024).

It is believed that cowpea reached southwestern Asia about 2300BC and was introduced to southern Europe early enough for the Greeks and Romans to grow it under the names *Phaseolus* and *Phaselus* (Allavena and Rosseti, 1986). It's supposed that cowpea reached India more than 200 thousand years ago from east Africa through the Sabenia lane along with other crops like sorghum, finger millets and bulrush – millet. Cowpea was introduced to the new world in the late seventieth century by the Spanish with more cultivars transported there from West Africa through the slave trade (Chourera *et al.*, 1995).

2.0 Materials and

Methods Plant Materials

Two(2) varieties of local cowpea (Kanannado and Danila) obtained from Ajingi Local Government Area of Kano State, were used as donor materials for this study. Kano is located on the latitude 11.6°N and longitude 8.3°E with tropical type of climate characterized by two distinct seasons, wet and dry.

2.1 Experimental site for the *In-vitro* Study

The study was carried out in the Plant Biotechnology laboratory of Jigawa Research Institute, Kazaure, Jigawa State, Nigeria.

2.2 Seed Sterilization

The seeds were washed four (4) times in running tap water, followed by immersion in 70% ethanol for two (2) minutes and

sterilized by immersion in 20% commercial bleach (5% sodium hypochlorite). This was followed by addition of few drops of tween 20 with rigorous shaking at three (3) minute interval. Tween 20 ensures contact between the hypochlorite and seed. Finally, the seeds were rinsed three (3) times in double distilled water.

2.3 Medium and Culture Conditions

The medium used in this study was Murashige and Skoog (MS) (Murashige and Skoog, 1962) basal medium, which consist of macro and micro-salt and vitamins. The medium was supplemented with 30% sucrose, pH was adjusted to 5.8 with 1M KOH and solidified with 8% agar before autoclaving for 15 minutes at 121°C. All cultures were incubated at 27 ± 2°C.

Composition of Murashige and Skoog (1962) Basal Medium

Macro – elements	Concentration (mg/l/L)
NH ₄ NO ₃	1650
KNO ₃	1900
CaCl ₂ .2H ₂ O	440
KH ₂ PO ₄	170
Mg/ISO ₄ .7H ₂ O	370
Micro – elements	Concentration (mg/l/L)
H ₃ BO ₃	6.20
NaEDTA.2H ₂ O	37.30
MnSO ₄ .4H ₂ O	22.30
FeSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	27.8
ZnSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	8.6
KI	0.83
Na ₂ MgO ₂ .2H ₂ O	0.25
CuSO ₄ .5H ₂ O	0.025
CaCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	0.025
Vitamins	Concentration (mg/l/L)
Myoinositol	100
Nicotinic acid	0.5
Pyridoxine-HCl	0.5
Thiamine-HCl	0.5
Glycine	2.0
Carbon Source	Concentration (mg/l/L)
Sucrose	30,000

3.0 Embryo Culture

Complete embryos were excised by the use of forceps and surgical blade. The cotyledons were first opened, then the embryo were excised and placed in culture bottles containing 35ml of the medium and the bottles were sealed with paraffin film. The culture bottles were then incubated in a growth chamber at $27 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, under 18 hour photoperiod for fourteen (14) days.

Shoot apices with average length of 1cm were evaluated and recorded. These apices can be excised in future study to produce shoots *in vitro* from the *in vitro* seedlings and used as explants.

4.0 Results

Shoot apices development was recorded in 50% of the induction media after oneweek of incubation under sixteen hours photoperiod. Shoot apices development was observed in 70% of the cultures after two (2) weeks of incubation. Development of multiple shoots apices ranging from 2 to 4 shoots in few cultures (and about 4 shoots in two (2) cultures) was observed after three weeks of culture.

Statistical analysis showed that there were significant ($P < 0.0001$) differences among the hormone supplements, and genotypes in terms of the number of shoots produced. However, no significant difference was observed among the experiment replications and

interactions between the hormone supplements and genotypes.

The result showed that, Danilla was the highest with 90% of the explants producing single or multiple shoots apices. The least among the genotypes was Kanannado with 75% response.

4.1 Summary and Conclusion

Regeneration of cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*(L.) Walp) cultivars; Kanannado and Danila via organogenesis was conducted using Shoot apices explant cultured on Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium. Differences were observed in response of explants from different cowpea cultivar, to organogenesis

In conclusion, induction of shoots apices on MS supplemented with 35% sucrose was achieved in local cowpea varieties used in this study. However, none of these regenerated shoots reached the length of 3cm. This protocol could also be modified and adapted for propagation of other elite cultivars of cowpea. It could also serve as a spring board for further research on the *in vitro* transformation of important traits in cowpea.

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